

A GENERAL EVALUATION OF THE POTENTIAL ANTHELMINTIC EFFECT OF *Mespilus germanica* L. FRUIT ETHANOL EXTRACT ON *Caenorhabditis elegans*

Keywords

Mespilus germanica,

Anthelmintic activity,

Caenorhabditis elegans,

Ethnobotany,

Medicinal plants

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ABSTRACT

Gastrointestinal nematode infections cause significant economic and health problems in developing countries. Although anthelmintic drugs commonly used today, such as albendazole, mebendazole, and levamisole, are effective, resistance in parasites has become widespread as a result of long-term use. This situation has encouraged the discovery of new naturally sourced anthelmintic agents, with medicinal plants rich in phytochemical compounds becoming a focus of scientific interest. The species *Mespilus germanica* L. has many uses, both gastronomically and traditionally. The model organism we use, *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*), has recently become the preferred choice for anthelmintic activity studies due to the ease of its working conditions, its genetic structure, its use in numerous pharmacological and toxicological studies, and the similarity of its neuromuscular and molecular pathways to those of parasitic helminths. According to World Health Organization (WHO) data, 60% of developing countries do not have easy access to anthelmintic drugs. People in developing countries still use herbal medicines and traditional treatment methods to treat intestinal worm infections. There are not many studies in the literature on the anthelmintic effect of *Mespilus germanica* L.. Only a few ethnobotanical studies have been identified in Turkey. In particular, the identification of the active ingredients of *M. germanica* L. using different methods and testing these active ingredients for anthelmintic activity could be an important step for clinical studies in this field. Furthermore, it should not be overlooked that the growing environment and conditions of *M. germanica* fruit, as well as storage and preservation conditions, may affect the fruit's active ingredient content and quantity.

INTRODUCTION

Helminth infections remain one of the most prevalent parasitic diseases worldwide, affecting billions of people. Gastrointestinal nematode infections, in particular, cause significant economic and health problems in developing countries¹. Although commonly used anthelmintic drugs such as albendazole, mebendazole, and levamisole are effective, resistance development in parasites has become widespread as a result of long-term use². This situation has encouraged the discovery of new anthelmintic agents derived from natural sources, with medicinal plants rich in phytochemical components becoming a focus of scientific interest³.

The traditional and culinary use of *Mespilus germanica* L., a member of the Rosaceae family commonly known as “medlar,” dates back to the Assyrians, Babylonians, Greeks, and Romans. Although this species was a popular fruit tree and ornamental tree during the Middle Ages, it is now considered an underappreciated and overlooked fruit. The medlar fruit has many uses, both gastronomically and traditionally, and the fruit of the species is rich in organic acids, fatty acids, sugars, carotenoids, amino acids, vitamins, and essential elements⁴.

The fruit of this species, which blooms in May and June, is initially hard and green to reddish brown. The fruit has a bitter taste due to its high tannin content and is not suitable for fresh consumption. When stored in cool, dry, and dark conditions, the fruit undergoes a natural softening process called bletting, making it edible. As they ripen, the fruits turn brown, soften in texture, and take on a flavor reminiscent of cooked apples or fruit puree. In traditional medicine, various parts of *M. germanica*, including its fruit, leaves, wood, and bark, have been used to treat a wide variety of ailments affecting the digestive system, kidneys, intestines, and metabolic disorders such as diabetes. The fruit is traditionally considered effective in alleviating conditions such as diarrhea, cough, rheumatism, hemorrhoids, asthma, constipation, kidney and bladder stones, hepatitis,

Volume: 3

Issue: 3

Page: 157– 161

Received: 11.07.2025

Accepted: 30.09.2025

Available online: 21.10.2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17431599

stomach bloating, and menstrual irregularities⁵. It also contains significantly more minerals than other fruits, has a low sugar content, and is rich in vitamins. The medlar fruit is a rich source of polyphenolic compounds, particularly phenolic acids⁶.

In our study, we used *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*) as a model organism. Due to the ease of its experimental conditions, its genetic structure, its use in numerous pharmacological and toxicological studies, and the similarity of its neuromuscular and molecular pathways to those of parasitic helminths, it has become the preferred organism in antihelminthic activity studies in recent years⁷.

The aim of this study is to test whether the ethanol extract of *Mespilus germanica* L., which has phenolic compounds and especially tannins, has antihelminthic potential using the *C. elegans* model organism. The results obtained will contribute significantly to both elucidating the antiparasitic effect mechanisms of phenolic compounds and revealing the pharmaceutical potential of Turkey's flora.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Plant Materials and Preparation of Plant Extracts

The *Mespilus germanica* L. samples used in the study were collected in 2025 from their natural habitat in Zile district, Tokat (Turkey) during the fruit ripening period. The species was identified by Assoc. Prof. Dr. Hülya Özpınar, a faculty member of the Department of Pharmaceutical Botany, Faculty of Pharmacy, Sivas Cumhuriyet University. The plant material was dried in the shade at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C) and mechanically ground into a fine powder. For the ethanol extract, 50 g of plant powder was macerated in 500 mL of 70% ethanol for 48 hours at room temperature in a shaker.

The extract was then filtered through filter paper, and the solvents were removed from the filtrates at 40 °C under low pressure using a rotary evaporator (Heidolph Hei-VAP Precision, Germany). The extracts were then freeze-dried using a lyophilizer (Labconco FreeZone 2.5). The dried extracts were stored in sterile vials at -20 °C.

C. elegans Culture Procedures

Solid culture medium was used in the experiments. For this purpose, NGM agar medium, referred to as standard Nematode Growth Medium (NGM), was prepared.

Preparation of Luria Broth

BactoTryptone (5 g), Yeast Extract (2.5 g), NaCl (5 g), and 1 M Tris (5 mL) were weighed and dissolved in 500 mL of deionized water. It was autoclaved at 125°C for 15 minutes and then cooled.

Preparation of *Escherichia coli* OP50 Strain

Escherichia coli OP50 strain was added to the prepared Luria Broth and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

Preparation of Nematode Growth Media (NCM)

Weigh NaCl (3 g), peptone (2.5 g), and agar (20 g) on a precision balance and dissolve in 1 L of deionized water. Autoclave at 125°C for 15 minutes, then cool to 55°C. Previously prepared and filtered through 0.2 µm pore filters, 1 mL of 1 M CaCl₂, 1 mL of 5 mg/mL cholesterol, 1 mL of 1 M MgSO₄, and 25 mL of 1 M KPO₄ (pH: 6) were added to the medium and homogenized. The medium pH was adjusted to 6. The NGMs containing the extract were kept at 55 °C until they were ready for use.

Production of *C. elegans*

For the production and passage of *C. elegans*, 10 mL of NGM prepared for this purpose was transferred to 6 mm diameter Petri dishes and allowed to solidify at room temperature. 200 µL of the produced *E. coli* OP50 strain was added on top and allowed to dry. *C. elegans* were passaged and propagated in the petri dishes.

Synchronization of *C. elegans*

Approximately 10 adult *C. elegans* were transferred to an NGM Petri dish containing bacteria. After six hours of oviposition, the adult *C. elegans* were removed from the petri dish. These eggs produced synchronized larvae. These were used in the study when they reached the adult stage at the end of the third day.

Determination of Anthelmintic Activity

Mespilus germanica fruit extracts were prepared separately in sterile 200 mL beakers and added to NGM previously prepared at concentrations of 100 mg/mL, 50 mg/mL, 25 mg/mL, and 12.5 mg/mL and kept in liquid form at 55 °C. The mixture was then homogenized under sterile conditions. To prevent nematode reproduction throughout their life cycle, 10 mL of the medium obtained was distributed into 6 mm diameter Petri dishes under sterile conditions and allowed to solidify at room temperature. Subsequently, 200 µL of *E. coli* OP50 strain was added to each dish and allowed to dry. The positive control group was prepared at a concentration of 50 mg/mL Albendazole (Andazol 200 mg tablet, Biofarma), while no active substance was added to the negative control group.

Four petri dishes were prepared for each concentration. Ten synchronized adult *C. elegans* were transferred to the petri dishes under a stereomicroscope. The nematodes were evaluated for paralysis and mortality at 6, 12, and 24 hours. Morphological changes were also observed microscopically. The study was repeated three times at 22 °C.

Statistical Analysis

In addition to the One Way ANOVA test, Tukey's test was used for the statistical analysis of the obtained data. For this purpose, the SPSS 16.0 (SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA) statistical program was used, and a $p < 0.05$ value at a 95% confidence interval was considered statistically significant between groups.

RESULTS

Evaluation of the Anthelmintic Effect of *Mespilus germanica* L. Fruit Ethanol Extract

Each group in the experiment consisted of 50 individuals. The fruit ethanol extracts of *Mespilus germanica* at concentrations of 12.5 mg/mL, 25 mg/mL, 50 mg/mL, and 100 mg/mL were examined for their effects on both paralysis and mortality rates in *C. elegans* individuals. When the dose-dependent paralysis rate was examined, it was found that the paralysis rate was higher with increasing concentration.

Concentration (mg/mL)	Paralysis Rate (%)		
	6 hours	12 hours	24 hours
12.5	39 ± 0.6	60 ± 0.4	72 ± 0.3
25	65 ± 0.3	77 ± 0.2	81 ± 0.2
50	83 ± 0.2	87 ± 0.1	89 ± 0.1
100	98 ± 0.1	100 ± 0.1	100 ± 0.05
Positive Control (Albendazole 50 mg/mL)	100 ± 0.0	100 ± 0.0	100 ± 0.0
Negative Control	0 ± 0.0	0 ± 0.0	0 ± 0.0

Table 1. Dose-dependent paralysis rates of *Mespilus germanica* L. fruit ethanol extract on *C. elegans* individuals

Table 1 shows that, based on these data, paralysis exceeding 90% was achieved within the first 6 hours, particularly at a concentration of 100 mg/mL, while paralysis rates continued to increase up to 24 hours at lower concentrations. This observation provides information about the rapid and persistent effect of the extract.

When mortality rates were examined, they increased in terms of both concentration and duration. At a concentration of 100 mg/mL, 99% mortality was reached after 24 hours, while at lower concentrations, the mortality rate increased over time. At a concentration of 12.5 mg/mL, only 25% mortality was observed after 6 hours, while this rate reached 57% after 24 hours (Table 2).

In our study, albendazole, used as a positive control, exerts its

activity by affecting the vital functions of helminths, particularly their energy metabolism. As clearly shown in Table 2, albendazole caused 100% mortality after 12 hours, while the *M. germanica* fruit ethanol extract showed a mortality rate of 96% after 12 hours. At a dose of 100 mg/mL, a very high mortality rate of 99% was observed after 24 hours. While no paralysis or mortality was observed in the negative control, the paralysis and mortality rates observed at different doses in our study group prove that the effects are dependent on the extracts and their doses.

In deceased individuals, criteria such as deformation and complete loss of the pharyngeal pumping reflex are considered death reactions; whereas in paralysis, functions such as slowed

pharyngeal pumping movement, loss of dorso-ventral movement, and immobility are used as a basis for evaluation.

When the data were statistically evaluated, it was observed that the antihelminthic effect of *M. germançca* fruit ethanol extract on the *C. elegans* model organism appeared in a time-

and dose-dependent manner. The results of the two-way analysis of variance (Two-way ANOVA) showed that the effects of both the concentrations used and the experimental groups were statistically significant in terms of both paralysis and mortality rates ($p < 0.001$).

Concentration (mg/mL)	Mortality Rate (%)		
	6 hours	12 hours	24 hours
12.5	25±1.8	37±2.3	57±1.2
25	58±1.4	61±1.4	74±1.0
50	79±1.5	89±1.7	92±1.6
100	95±0.9	96±0.6	99±0.8
Positive Control (Albendazole 50 mg/mL)	98± 0.9	100±0.0	100±0.0
Negative Control	0± 0.0	0± 0.0	0± 0.0

Table 2. Dose-dependent mortality rates of *C. elegans* individuals exposed to *Mespğus germançca* L. fruit ethanol extract

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

According to World Health Organization (WHO) data, 60% of developing countries still lack easy access to antihelminthic drugs. People in developing countries still use herbal medicines and traditional treatment methods to treat intestinal worm infections. Side effects of currently used synthetic drugs include nausea, dizziness, and digestive disorders. Among treatment methods with antihelminthic effects, characteristics such as single-dose administration, lack of host toxicity, low cost, and clinical treatment capability are particularly desirable⁸.

In recent years, numerous studies have been conducted on the antihelminthic effects of various plant extracts under in vitro and in vivo conditions. In particular, the mechanisms of action of various plant extracts that could serve as alternatives to synthetic drugs are being investigated⁹. Molecular methods are among the promising approaches for the in vivo and in vitro diagnosis of many parasitic infections. These methods may be particularly effective in detecting parasitic nematodes and antihelminthic resistance. The discovery of resistance mechanisms may help reduce antihelminthic drug resistance in parasites and diagnose drug resistance associated with genomic changes, thereby preventing unnecessary treatment methods and reducing many potential complications¹⁰.

There are not many studies in the literature on the antihelminthic effect of *Mespğus germançca* L. ethnobotanical records indicate that the fresh fruits of the species are consumed on an empty stomach in Dereli, Giresun (Turkey) to treat intestinal parasites in humans, and that a decoction prepared from the bark of the species is used as a vermifuge in animals in Şile, Istanbul (Turkey)¹¹.

In general, many plant secondary metabolites, including tannins, chalcones, coumarins, terpenoids, alkaloids, antioxidants, and flavonoids, possess antihelminthic and neurotoxic properties and exert their effects by inhibiting mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation. Studies have shown that these plant-based compounds exhibit higher biological activity than synthetic compounds. Plants have been used for generations to treat parasitic diseases in many regions of the world and are still used today. According to one study, between 2000 and 2019, 40 patents were granted for natural product-based nematicides divided into seven structural classes, but none of these are yet commercially available on the market¹⁰. The isolation and identification of active ingredients that exhibit antihelminthic activity, particularly in plants, and the determination of whether there is a relationship between these substances remain open topics for research.

C. elegans is used as a model organism in studies due to its apathogenic nature, ease of cultivation in laboratory settings,

and low workload in research. However, it can be considered among the newly applied methods in antihelminthic activity studies¹².

Studies on the chemical composition of *Mespilus germanica* L. have identified active compounds such as caffeic acid, ferulic acid, syringic acid, ellagic acid, quercetin, α -tocopherol, pyrogallol, p-hydroxybenzoic acid, vanillin, p-coumaric acid, gallic acid, and ascorbic acid have been identified in the species¹³. The fruit contains condensed tannins, which give it a bitter taste¹⁴. In terms of flavor, phenolic compounds are the main substances responsible for the bitter taste in fruit, and among these compounds, tannins, catechins, and epicatechins have been identified as bitterness molecules¹⁵. There are numerous studies suggesting that condensed tannins may be effective in antihelminthic activity^{16,17}. In a study investigating the effects of condensed tannins on the motility and morphology of adult *Oesophagostomum dentatum*, an extract rich in condensed tannins from walnut shells was found to inhibit the motility of adult *O. dentatum*. Furthermore, examination of thin sections of adult worms exposed to condensed tannins using transmission electron microscopy revealed that it was observed that the cuticle layer of the worms was rough and the hypodermis was torn and separated¹⁸.

Our experimental study holds an important place in the literature, given the limited number of experimental studies on the antihelminthic effect of *Mespilus germanica* L. In particular, the identification of the active ingredients of *M. germanica* L. using different methods and the testing of these active ingredients for antihelminthic activity could form an important step for clinical studies in this field. Furthermore, it should not be overlooked that the growing environment and conditions of *M. germanica* fruit, as well as storage and preservation conditions, may affect the fruit's active ingredient content and quantity.

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